

INTEGRAL CONDITION FOR BENNEY-LUKE TYPE EQUATION THE PROBLEM GIVEN WITH THE RIGHT AND INVERSE PROBLEM

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Abstract. The article studies the fractional order equation of the form $D_t^\alpha u(t) + A(D_t^\alpha u(t)) + A^2(D_t^\alpha u(t)) + Au(t) = f$, where $0 < \alpha < 1$, for the time interval $0 < t \leq T$ with the integral boundary condition $\int_0^T u(t)dt = \varphi$. Here, $A: H \rightarrow H$ is a self-adjoint, unbounded, positive operator defined on a separable Hilbert space H , and A^{-1} is a compact operator. The article demonstrates the existence and uniqueness of solutions to the problem using the Fourier method. Additionally, it addresses the inverse problem concerning the determination of the right-hand side of the equation.

Key words. Integral, boundary condition, Benney-Luke equation, Hilbert, orthogonal.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается задача нахождения решения дробно-ординариес уравнения вида $D_t^\alpha u(t) + A(D_t^\alpha u(t)) + A^2(D_t^\alpha u(t)) + Au(t) = f$, где $0 < \alpha < 1$, на временном интервале $0 < t \leq T$ с интегральным краевым условием $\int_0^T u(t)dt = \varphi$. Оператор $A: H \rightarrow H$ является самосопряженным, неограниченным, положительным оператором, определенным в сепарабельном гильбертовом пространстве H , а A^{-1} является компактным оператором. В статье с использованием метода Фурье показана существование и единственность решения задачи. Кроме того, рассматривается обратная задача, связанная с определением правой части уравнения.

Ключевые слова: интеграл, граничное условие, уравнение типа Бенни-Лука, Гильберт, ортогональный.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada $D_t^\alpha u(t) + A(D_t^\alpha u(t)) + A^2(D_t^\alpha u(t)) + Au(t) = f$, $0 < \alpha < 1$, ko'rinishidagi kasr tartibli tenglama uchun vaqt bo'yicha $0 < t \leq T$, $\int_0^T u(t)dt = \varphi$ integral chegaraviy shartni qanotlantruvchi yechimni topish masalasi o'rganilgan, $A: H \rightarrow H$ o'z-o'ziga qo'shma, chegaralanmagan, musbat H separabel Hilbert fazosida aniqlangan operator va A^{-1} kompakt operator. Maqolada Furye usulidan foydalanib masalaning yechimi mavjudligi va yagonaligi ko'rsatilgan. Bundan tashqari maqolada tenglamaning o'ng tomonini topish bo'yicha teskari masala ham o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Integral, chegaraviy shart, Benney-Luke tipidagi tenglama, Hilbert, ortogonal

Let H be a separable Hilbert space with the scalar product $(\cdot, \cdot)$ and the norm $\|\cdot\|$. Let the operator $A: H \rightarrow H$ be a self-adjoint, positive, unbounded arbitrary operator with the domain of definition $D(A)$. Suppose that operator A has a complete orthonormal system of eigenfunctions $\{v_k\}$ in the space H and the corresponding set of positive eigenvalues $\{\lambda_k\}$. We can renumber eigenvalues non-descendingly, that is, write $0 < \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots \rightarrow +\infty$

Let a vector-function (or simply function) $h(t)$ be defined in the interval $[0, +\infty)$ with values in H . We will consider the Caputo fractional derivative of order $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ which is defined as (see, e.g., [1]-[2])

$$D_t^\alpha h(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \sum_0^t \frac{h'(\xi)}{(t-\xi)^\alpha} d\xi, \quad t > 0.$$

Let $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ is a given number. The main problem in this paper is the following non-local problem

$$\begin{cases} D_t^\alpha u(t) + A(D_t^\alpha u(t)) + A^2(D_t^\alpha u(t)) + Au(t) = f(t), & 0 \leq t \leq T, \\ \int_0^T u(t) dt = \varphi, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where elements $\varphi, f \in H$. We call this problem the forward problem.

We allow parameter α to take the value 1, i.e., the equation in (1) can go to the classical equation,

since the results obtained in this work are also new for such equations

Definition. A function $u(t) \in C((0, T]; H)$ is called the solution of the forward problem if it has properties

$A^2(D_t^\alpha u(t)), A(D_t^\alpha u(t)), D_t^\alpha u(t), Au(t) \in C((0, T]; H)$ and satisfies the conditions of problem (1)

Denote by $E_{\tau, \mu}(z)$ the two-parameter Mittag-Leffler function

$$E_{\tau, \mu}(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\Gamma(\tau n + \mu)},$$

where $\tau > 0$ and μ is an arbitrary complex number. If $\mu = 1$ then we have the classical Mittag-Leffler function

$$E_{\tau, \mu}(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\tau k + 1)} = E_\tau(z),$$

The main result of this paper reads as follows

Theorem. Let $\phi \in D(A)$ and $f \in H$. The problem (1) has a unique solution and the solution can be represented as a series converging uniformly in t

$$\begin{aligned} u(t) = & \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{E_{\alpha, 2}(-\mu_k T^\alpha) T} (\phi_k E_{\alpha, 1}(-\mu_k t^\alpha) \\ & + \frac{f_k}{1 + \lambda_k + \lambda_k^2} [t^\alpha E_{\alpha, \alpha+1}(-\mu_k t^\alpha) E_{\alpha, 2}(-\mu_k T^\alpha) T - E_{\alpha, 1}(-\mu_k t^\alpha) E_{\alpha, \alpha+2}(-\mu_k T^\alpha) T^{\alpha+1}]) \nu_k \end{aligned}$$

whert f_k, ϕ_k are the Fourier coefficients of the functions $\mu_k = \frac{\lambda_k}{1 + \lambda_k + \lambda_k^2}$

In addition to the forward problem, the article also studies the inverse problem of finding the right-hand side of the equation. Let us consider the inverse problem

$$u(\tau) = \Psi, \quad 0 < \tau \leq T \quad (2)$$

in which the unknown element $f \in H$, characterizing the action of heat sources, does not depend on $u(t)$ and $\Psi, \phi \in H$ are given elements.

Definition. A pair $\{u(t), f\}$ of function $u(t) \in C((0, T]; H)$ and $f \in H$ with the properties $A^2(D_t^\alpha u(t)), A(D_t^\alpha u(t)), D_t^\alpha u(t)$ and $Au(t) \in C((0, T]; H)$ and satisfying conditions (1), (2) is called the solution of the inverse problem (1), (2).

Theorem . Let $\phi, \Psi \in D(A)$. Then the inverse problem (1), (2) has a unique solution $\{u(t), f\}$ and this solution has the following form

$$u(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{E_{\alpha,2}(-\mu_k T^\alpha) T} (\phi_k E_{\alpha,1}(-\mu_k t^\alpha) + \frac{f_k}{1 + \lambda_k + \lambda_k^2} [t^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha+1}(-\mu_k t^\alpha) E_{\alpha,2}(-\mu_k T^\alpha) T - E_{\alpha,1}(-\mu_k t^\alpha) E_{\alpha,\alpha+2}(-\mu_k T^\alpha) T^{\alpha+1}]) v_k$$

where and

$$f = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} f_k v_k$$

$$f_k = \frac{\Psi_k E_{\alpha,2}(-\mu_k T^\alpha) T - \phi_k E_{\alpha,1}(-\mu_k \tau^\alpha)}{\tau^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha+1}(-\mu_k t^\alpha) E_{\alpha,2}(-\mu_k T^\alpha) T - E_{\alpha,1}(-\mu_k t^\alpha) E_{\alpha,\alpha+2}(-\mu_k T^\alpha) T^{\alpha+1}} (1 + \lambda_k + \lambda_k^2).$$

REFERENCES

1. C.Lizama, Abstract linear fractional evolution equations, Handbook of Fractional Calculus with Applications V. 2, J.A.T. Machado Ed. DeGruyter, 465-497 (2019)
2. R.Gorenflo, A.A.Kilbas, F.Mainardi and S.V.Rogozin, Mittag-Leffler Functions, Related Topics and Applications; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, (2014), doi: 10.1007/978 3-662-61550-8. [CrossRef]